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Impact of Principal's Attitude on Female Teacher's PerformanceSabika Alisher Zaidi¹

Being the head of school, principals use several motivational strategies to enhance teacher's performance in the process of learning. Principal's continuous support and encouragement persuades the teachers to perform well. In order to work efficiently teachers need motivation, relax working environment, informal meetings, easy access to principals, monetary and non-monetary appraisals etc. This study aims to see the impact of principal's attitude on teacher's performance. Data is collected through random sampling. Primary school teachers working in 25 private schools of Liaquatnabad Town, Karachi were the population of study. 300 primary school teachers were selected at random. Data was collected through Likert Scale questionnaire comprised of 3 hypothesis and 15 items on a scale of 1 till 4. Data shows significant difference among factors such as relax working hours, informal meetings, trainings, access to principal etc. Verbal and nonverbal appreciation with some monetary reward is recommended.

Keywords: Motivation, Strategies, Learning, Monetary, Appreciation

Introduction

Principals are the school leaders. Principals perform various functions such as administration, organizing, staffing, motivating, leading, training, evaluating teacher's performance, job appraisals, budgeting etc. Their most important task is to maintain smooth running of education system within school with utmost efficiency. In order to achieve the goal of efficient and effective school system they have to keep the building pillars of school strong and aligned with each other. These building pillars are the teachers. Principals motivate the teachers towards the achievement of established goals by supporting them to adjust with the changing environment of school. (Green, 2001). An effective principal can lead the process of change successfully. (Hamida Zafar et al, 2019). There are certain strategies, traits and believes that school

principals can apply in order to improve teacher's performance. A strong motivation can be one of those strategies in order to persuade teachers to work effectively. It is very important to improve teacher's performance (Hamidi, et al 2019) because they have to perform strategic role to develop the learner's potential. Performance is considered the coinciding of requirement of job with the execution of job. (Rue and Byars (2007) .In order to boost teacher's performance some external and internal factors are required (Jaja Sudarjat, et al 2015). External factors may include Salary, Relax working hours, Residing near the work place and internal factors may include words of encouragement, easy access to principal, informal meeting etc.

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Literature Review

Quality leadership is responsible for the progress of school. (Blasé and Blasé, 2000). Modern school systems require more liberal and democratic way of leadership. They are not supposed to be rigid and authoritative if they want to build a strong positive relationship with their staff members. This changing environment expect them to be more optimistic, open minded, democratic, appreciative, problem solver and humanistic.

School leadership is the supervision of teacher's professional activities so they can guide students in much better way. (Syaeful Sagala, 2006) Teachers need constant motivation, appreciation and recognition from their supervisors. Teacher's keen interest in teaching and their passion creates a bond between teacher and student. Teacher's personal interest in teaching improves students' liking for learning, energy, creativity and curiosity. Teacher's work is motivation for them and for their students. (Patrick et al., 2000). There are two types of motivation. Intrinsic and extrinsic. Doing an activity because it is interesting and pleasurable is called intrinsic motivation to do something. (Mekler et al., 2017). On the other hand, extrinsic motivation comes out of external factors such as status, appreciation, or promotion (Deci, 1971). External derives can be monetary or non monetary rewards such as retirement plans, health insurance, and permissions (Newstrom & Davis, 2002).

Researchers have also examined factors affecting teacher motivation. It includes the general climate of the school, class sizes, school resources and facilities, institutional activities, peer relations, the definition of the teacher's role, expectations of students, the leadership structure of the school, educational programming, time management, physical environment conditions, wages, rewards, incentives, job design, and performance management systems

(Daniels, 2016; Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2013; Rasheed et al., 2016).

Specifically female teachers face certain problems in their professional career in Pakistan which hinders their performance and growth. Problems of female school teachers includes problems due to social pressure, problems due to economic conditions, problems due to household activities, problems due to political interference, social recognition, of lodging and amenities, frequent transfer, professional development, school culture, community involvement, over loaded classes, physical and learning resources, supervision, coordination cooperation, delivery pregnancy etc. (Syed Farooq Shah et al. (2014)

Based on the literature review and above discussion researcher will find out the effect of principal's attitude on teachers performance.

Research problem

This study is focused on finding out the impact of principal's attitude on female teacher's performance in Karachi.

Objective of the study

To assess the behavior and attitude of school principals in order to enhance teacher's performance to improve learner's potential.

Research Question

- What monetary and non-monetary factors affect the motivation of female teachers?
- Does the relax working environment affect the performance of female teachers?
- Does the friendly attitude of principal help female teachers to utilize their potential at maximum?

Hypothesis

- Ho1 = Monetary and non-Monetary factors have no significant impact on Female Teacher's Performance.
- Ho2=Relax Working Environment has no significant impact on Female Teachers Performance.
- Ho3= Direct Supervision of Principal has no significant impact on Female Teachers Performance.

Data Analysis and Methodology

Data is collected through random sampling. Primary school teachers working in 25 private schools of Liaquatabad Town, Karachi were the population of study. 300 primary school teachers were selected at random. Data was collected through Likert Scale questionnaire comprised of 3 hypothesis and 15 items on a scale of 1 till 4.

Correlation is applied on the data to evaluate the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
MnMC_1	300	9	36	29.73	6.732
WEC_2	300	5	20	16.45	3.977
DSC_3	300	9	36	29.63	7.232
Teacher Performance	300	1	4	1.86	.406
Valid N (listwise)	300				

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Correlations			
		WEC_2	Teacher Performance
WEC_2	Pearson Correlation	1	-.131*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.023
	N	300	300
Teacher Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.131*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.023	
	N	300	300

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlations			
		DSC_3	Teacher Performance
DSC_3	Pearson Correlation	1	-.143*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.013
	N	300	300
Teacher Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.143*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.013	
	N	300	300

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Result and Conclusion

Data is analyzed through correlation which shows that monetary appraisals, working environment and Direct Supervision has positive correlation which means Principals attitude has positive impact on all three variables.

References

Blase, J., & Blase, J. (1999). Principals’ instructional leadership and teacher development:

Teachers’ perspectives. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 35(3), 349-378. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X99353003>

Byars, L. and Rue, L. (2011) *Human Resource Management*. McGraw-Hill, New York.

Deci, E. L. (1971). Effects of externally mediated rewards on intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 18(1), 105-115. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0030644>

Green, R. L. (2001). *Practicing the art of leadership. A problem-based approach to implementing the*

- ISLLC standards. Upper saddle River, NJ: Merrill Prentice Hall
- Hamida Zafar,T.A.,Sajjad Hayat Akhtar.(2019). The Changing Approaches of Secondary School Principals about Their Roles and Responsibilities in Pakistan. *Academic Research International* Vol. 10(4),154-160.
- Newstrom, J. W., & Davis, K (2002). *Organizational behaviour: Human behaviour at work* (11th ed.). Mc-GrawHill
- Patrick, B. C., Hisley, J., & Kempler, T. (2000). "What's everybody so excited about?": The effects of teacher enthusiasm on student intrinsic motivation and vitality. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 68(3), 217- 236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220970009600093>